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THE IMPORTANCE OF THE CORPORATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE WORLD ECONOMY

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Abstract. *In the development of the world economy, the importance of the corporation, the opportunity for investment, the reduction of poverty, and the role of providing a source of income for the employed are gaining high importance. In this article, we will dwell on the role and importance of investments in the development of the world economy.*

Key words. *Investment, corporation, labor resources, employment.*

In the development of the world economy, the importance of the corporation, the opportunity for investment, the reduction of poverty, and the role of providing a source of income for the employed are gaining high importance. "In developed countries, the share of corporations in the country's GDP is between 20-40 percent. In particular, in Korea - 24.2 percent, in the USA - 38.9 percent, in Great Britain - 19 percent, in Germany - 30.2 percent, in Finland - 20 percent, in the Netherlands - 25 percent". In the conditions of today's globalization, special importance is given to improving the activities of corporations based on crowdfunding, crowdlending, crowdinvesting, increasing their role and share in the economy, and introducing innovative technologies.

Taking into account the high nature of corporations to economic liberalization in the world, scientific researches are being carried out by international scientific research organizations regarding the support of corporations by the state, in particular,

new modern methods of making investments in this field, increasing the effectiveness of their investments. Attracting private investments to corporations, promotion of direct investments and in-depth research of scientific and practical aspects of development of the country's national economy are considered urgent scientific problems in the conditions of Uzbekistan.

The main issues of the development of corporations today are as follows:

- development of an author's approach based on the research of the development of scientific views dedicated to increasing the efficiency of the investment policy of corporations;
- a comparative comparison of the world practice of increasing the efficiency of the investment policy of corporations;
- assessment of investment dynamics aimed at improving the effectiveness of the investment policy of corporations;
- to improve the practice of assessing the investment potential of corporations;
- to improve the effectiveness of the investment policy of corporations in the long-term perspective and to determine the possibilities of its innovative development;
- development of scientific proposals and practical recommendations for increasing the efficiency of state programs aimed at increasing the efficiency of the investment policy of corporations.

In Uzbekistan, comprehensive measures are being implemented to support the activities of corporations, give incentives to the industry, and increase the economic efficiency of investments. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in his open dialogue meeting with businessmen said that "...at the expense of the proposed mechanisms, 30-40 trillion rubles will be deposited in commercial banks every year on average." long-term additional resources in the national currency of soums will be formed. "... entrepreneurs have the opportunity to get loans in national currency for a long time and at least 5 percent cheaper than the current rates". In order to ensure the execution of these tasks, it is an urgent issue to carry out scientific research in the areas of the assessment practice approach to increase the economic efficiency of investments

in corporations, small businesses and private entrepreneurship, improvement based on innovative technologies, development based on the integration of production, infrastructure and scientific supply.

Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ORQ-598 of December 25, 2019 “On Investments and Investment Activities”, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 of January 28, 2022 “On the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026”, dated April 3, 2020 No. PF-5978 “On additional measures to support the population, economic sectors and business entities during the coronavirus pandemic”, Decree No. PF-6264 of July 19, 2021 “On measures to establish the strategic development agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan” and No. PQ-4026 of November 23, 2018 “On measures to strengthen the legal protection of creditors and improve mechanisms for financing business activities”, on April 29, 2019 No. PQ-4300 “On measures to further improve the mechanisms of attracting foreign direct investment to the economy of the Republic” and other regulatory legal documents related to this field serve to a certain extent in the implementation of tasks.

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